

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Araphid pennate diatoms of Ngor (Dakar, Senegal)

Gueye Madiop *

Laboratory of Botany and Biodiversity, Department of Plant Biology, Faculty of Sciences and Techniques, Cheikh Anta Diop University of Dakar, BP 5500, Dakar-Fann, Senegal.

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Abstract

The present study provides the first list of marine araphid pennate diatoms from Ngor (Senegal). A total of 18 taxa belonging to 9 genera, 9 families, and 8 orders of Fragilariophyceae Class were described and identified by light microscopy in Ngor's waters between July 2009 and November 2011. All these taxa are new for the microflora of Ngor.

Keywords: Diatoms; Araphid Pennate; Taxonomic Composition; Ngor; Senegal

1. Introduction

Diatoms are single-celled photosynthetic eukaryotes universally distributed in all types of aquatic environment. They are the most important group in terms of diversity, abundance and productivity in marine and continental environments [1]. Diatoms are important members of the phytoplankton as well as the benthic communities. It is estimated that these microalgae may account for 40 to 45 % of oceanic production making them more productive than all the world's rainforests. Diatom algae play an important role in global cycling of Silica and Carbon and in sustaining fisheries [2]. They are abundant, diverse, ubiquitous, and sensitive environmental indicators and, thus, have an enormous ecological importance [3]. However, despite their ecological importance, no morphological descriptive study relating to diatoms has been made in the marine waters of Ngor. Only inventory studies have been carried out in the Cape Verde peninsula by [4, 5]. Thus, the objective of this work is to describe and determine the taxonomic composition of pennate araphid diatoms from Ngor (Senegal).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Presentation of the study area

The study was carried out in Ngor, a commune located at the western tip of Dakar, at Senegal (Figure 1). Ngor constitutes a promontory which extends the head of the Cape Verde Peninsula into the Atlantic Ocean. Considered as the westernmost part of Africa, it covers an area of 4.5 km² and has the particularity of being located on a seaside site. Ngor, bounded from the northwest to the southwest by the Atlantic Ocean, consists of a village and an Island. Ngor Island is located in the Atlantic Ocean, 800 m from the Dakar coast at 14°45'30"N and 17°30'56"W. It is therefore located west of the village of Ngor in the middle of a protected bay and constituted by the Hawaiian flows with doleric texture of the quaternary basaltic volcanism of the Mamelles.

* Corresponding author: Gueye Madiop

Laboratory of Botany and Biodiversity, Department of Plant Biology, Faculty of Sciences and Techniques, Cheikh Anta Diop University of Dakar, BP 5500, Dakar-Fann, Senegal.

Figure 1 Location of Ngor

2.2. Sampling and observation

Sampling was carried out in marine waters, between the village and the island, from July 2009 and November 2011, with a plankton net and by scraping supports. Diatoms have been specially prepared to reveal the details of the ornamentation of the frustules. Sub-samples underwent a treatment of cleaning of the frustules by combination of calcination to chemical attack of the organic matter, before being mounted with Canada balsam to prepare permanent slides for microscopy. The systematic arrangement of the diatoms list was made by according to [1].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Description and identification of taxa

Phylum Bacillariophyta

Class Fragilariophyceae Round

- **Order** Fragilariales Silva
- **Family** Fragilariaceae Greville
- **Genus** *Opephora* Small

3.1.1. *Opephora pinnata* var. *lanceolata* Boyer (Figure 2A)

Valve lanceolate (length 25 μm , diameter 7 μm) with ribs slightly radiating, areolate; median zone wide. The species presents the same morphological characters as those described by [6].

3.1.2. *Opephora schwartzii* (Grunow) Petit ((Figure 2B))

Valve oval to almost linear (length 28 μm , diameter 8 μm) with rounded apex; lower apex narrower. Valvaire surface with coarse areolas perpendicular to the pseudoraphe (3 to 4 areolas/10 μm). [7, 8, 9] encountered a species with identical morphological characters to this specimen.

Ecology and distribution: littoral marine species, known in all the oceans.

- **Order** Licmophorales Round
- **Family** Licmophoraceae Kützing
- **Genus** *Licmophora* Agardh

3.1.3. *Licmophora dalmatica* var. *tenella* K. (Figure 2D)

Frustules broadly wedge-shaped with rounded corners; valves heteropolar (diameter 35 μm , length 65 μm) very finely striated (about 30/10 μm). This species was identified from the work of [10].

Ecology and distribution: widespread species.

3.1.4. *Licmophora ehrenbergii* (Kuetz.) Grun. ((Figure 2C)

Frustules narrowly wedge-shaped, with shallow septum. Valves elongated wedge-shaped (length 155 μm , diameter 18 μm), with straight edges, slightly swollen at the base, subcapitated. Striae very robust (8 to 10/10 μm). The same species was described by [6, 10].

Ecology and distribution: coastal species.

3.1.5. *Licmophora flabellata* (Carm.) Ag. (Figure 2 E-F)

Syn. : *Licmophora splendida* Wm. Sm.

Frustule narrow and slightly wedge-shaped with rudimentary septa. Valves narrowly lanceolate (length 70-90 μm , diameter 7 μm) with subcapitated apex, narrowed and swollen base; valves in flabellate colonies. Striae very fine, about 30/10 μm . [6, 8, 10] described the same species.

Ecology and distribution: marine species, coastal, benthic or planktonic.

Figure 2 A: *Opephora pinnata* var. *lanceolata*, valve view; B: *Opephora schwartzii*, valve view; C: *Licmophora ehrenbergii*, valve view; D: *Licmophora dalmatica* var. *tenella*, girdle view; *Licmophora flabellata* : cells grouped in a stipitate colony (E), in girdle view (F). Scale Bars=10 μm

- **Family** Raphoneidaceae Forti
- **Genus** *Delphineis* Andrews

3.1.6. *Delphineis surirella* Ehr. Andrews (Figure 3A)

Valves (length 15 μm , diameter 8 μm) almost rounded in small specimens, lanceolate, with rounded, obtuse apices. Transapical striae, (9 to 12/10 μm) parallel to midline or slightly radiating; areoles rounded in slightly wavy longitudinal lines. Pseudoraphe narrow, linear in its middle part and widened in awl under the poles. [9, 11, 12, 13] described this species with the same morphological characteristics.

Ecology and Distribution: common marine species.

3.1.7. *Delphineis surirella* var. *australis* (Petit) Navarro ((Figure 3B)

Differs from *Delphineis surirella* in its linear-elliptical valves and greater length (length 47 μm , diameter 17 μm) ; 6 striae/10 μm . It was identified through the works of [8, 14].

Ecology and distribution: marine species.

- **Order** Ardissonaeales Round
- **Family** Ardissonaeaceae Round
- **Genus** *Ardissonaea* De Notaris

3.1.8. *Ardissonaea fulgens* (Greville) (Figure 3 C-D)

Syn. : *Synedra fulgens* (Greville) W. Smith 185

Cells linear as long sticks (diameter 12 μm). Apices and median region slightly dilated. Marginal ribs parallel to the apical axis and well-marked. Fine striation but robust, 13-15 striae/10 μm . The identification of this species was made through the works of [15, 16].

Ecology and distribution: widespread species, marine, brackish, coastal and estuarine, in tropical to temperate waters.

3.1.9. *Ardissonaea robusta* (Ralfs) De Notaris & Baglietto (Figure 3E)

Syn.: *Synedra robusta* Walfs in Pritchard 1861

Cells linear-elliptical (diameter 30 μm). Valve margins straight or slightly curvilinear with obtuse attenuated apices. Apical axis and longitudinal bands well distinct. Robust transverse striae, 5 to 9/10 μm . This specimen is morphologically identical to those described by [10, 15, 17].

- **Order** Toxariales Round
- **Family** Toxariaceae Round
- **Genus** *Toxarium* Bailey

3.1.10. *Toxarium undulatum* Bailey (Figure 3F)

Syn.: *Synedra undulata* (Bailey) Gregory 1857

Figure 3 A: *Delphineis surirella*, valvaire view; B: *Delphineis surirella* var. *australis*, valve view; C-D: *Ardissonaea fulgens*, (C) median region dilated and (D) extremity dilated; E: *Ardissonaea robusta*: valve view with obtuse attenuated extremity; F: *Toxarium undulatum* with median region and rounded apex dilated. Scale Bars=10 μm

Cells more or less arcuated with wavy valve edges. Valves (length 260 μm , diameter 8 μm) widened in the middle; apex dilated and rounded. Ornamentation finely punctuated-striated. The specimen is morphologically identical to those encountered by [9, 15, 16]. Ecology and distribution: marine and estuarine species, common in tropical and subtropical waters.

- **Order** Thalassionematales Round
- **Family** Thalassionemataceae Round
- **Genus** *Thalassionema* Grunow

3.1.11. *Thalassionema bacillare* (Heiden) Kolbe (Figure 4A)

Valve (length 82 μm , diameter 4 μm) linear, slightly widened in the center with rounded apex. Area axial distinct; ornamentation formed by a row of marginal areoles (granules).

The specimen is morphologically identical to those described by [11, 18].

Ecology and distribution: species reported in the waters of warm regions.

- **Order** Rhabdonematales Round and Crawford
- **Family** Rhabdonemataceae Round and Crawford
- **Genus** *Rhabdonema* Kützing

3.1.12. *Rhabdonema adriaticum* Kuetz (Figure 4B)

Cells quadrangular in girdle view with rounded and hyalins corners. Valves linear-elliptical with transverse striae, 8-9/10 μm . Presence of many septa, pierced by three foramina, It presents the same morphological characters as those described by [9, 15, 17].

Ecology and distribution: cosmopolitan littoral species, rarer in cold seas.

3.1.13. *Rhabdonema punctatum* (Hawey & Bailey) Stodder ex Boyer (Figure 4C)

Quadrangular cells in connective view with rounded and hyalins corners. Girdle widened by numerous intercalar bands, as well as numerous septa and foramen. Striped ornamentation with regular punctuations.

Dimension: diameter 85 μm , length 145 μm .

The species was identified from the works of [9, 15].

Ecology and distribution: tropical coastal marine species.

- **Order** Striatellales Round
- **Family** Striatellaceae Kützing
- **Genus** *Grammatophora* Ehrenberg

3.1.14. *Grammatophora hamulifera* Kützing (Figure 4D)

Syn.: *Grammatophora angulosa* var. *hamulifera* Kuetz:

Frustule rectangular in cingular view with two septas finished in hook. Striae transapical and fine, 15 / 10 μm . Dimensions: length 23 μm , width 16 μm . This specimen was identified through the works of [19, 20].

Ecology and distribution: coastal species.

3.1.15. *Grammatophora marina* (Lyngbye) Kützing (Figure 4E)

Frustule rectangular (length 30 μm , width 18 μm) in connective view, linear-elliptical and swollen in the center with rounding in valve view. Septa slightly wavy (two undulations) and terminated by a nodule. 15 striae/10 μm . [7, 20] have identified this species.

Ecology and distribution: coastal species frequent in warm and temperate waters.

Figure 4 A: *Thalassionema bacillare*, valve view; B: *Rhabdonema adriaticum*, tabular frustule; C: *Rhabdonema punctatum*, tabular frustule; D: *Grammatophora hamulifera*, girdle view; I: *Grammatophora marina*, girdle view. Scale Bars=10 μ m

3.1.16. *Grammatophora oceanica* Ehrenberg (Figure 5A)

Frustules rectangular (length 27 μ m, width 10 μ m).in connective view. Septa with a slight undulation near the base and terminated in nodular formation. Valves linear, slightly bulged in the middle. Transapical stries finely punctuated, 25-28 in 10 μ m.

This description is identical to those of [7, 10, 16].

Ecology and distribution: cosmopolitan marine and brackish species.

3.1.17. *Grammatophora oceanica* f. *minuscula* Per. (Figure 5B)

It differs from *G. oceanica* only by its very small size and the specimen encountered is more or less square (side 15 μ m). The species was identified through the work of [10].

Ecology and distribution: very widespread species.

- **Order** Climacospheniales Round
- **Family** Climacospheniaceae Round
- **Genus** *Climacosphenia* Ehrenberg

3.1.18. *Climacosphenia moniligera* Ehrenberg ((Figure 5 C-D-E)

Figure 5 A: *Grammatophora oceanica*, girdle view; B: *Grammatophora oceanica* f. *minuscula*, girdle view; *Climacosphenia moniligera*: C-D: girdle view (E) valve view showing the partition. Scale Bars=10 μ m

Frustules very elongated wedge-shaped presenting along their entire length a partition pierced with long openings separated by fairly wide bands. Valves (length 190 µm) clavate, rounded, with two submarginal longitudinal lines. Striae punctate and relatively visible, 16 to 17 below, 19 to 20 above on the valves, 13 from above to below on the connectives.

[15, 21, 22, 23] made it possible to identify this species.

Ecology and distribution: coastal species more common in warm tropical and subtropical waters.

3.2. Taxonomic composition

The results of the study showed that 18 taxa of araphid pennate diatoms (Class Fragilariophyceae) belonging to 9 genera and divided into 9 families, 8 orders were observed. The families Striatellaceae, Licmophoraceae are dominant with respectively four and three species. *Grammatophora*, with 4 species, is the most representative genera followed by *Licmophora* with 3 species. The Genus *Rhabdonema*, *Ardissonia*, *Delphineis*, *Opephora* each have 2 species, the rest with one species.

These species are almost all marine and coastal; which explains their presence in the marine waters of Ngor.

Species like *Grammatophora hamulifera*, *Grammatophora marina*, *Delphineis surirella*, *Delphineis surirella* var. *australis*, *Opephora schwartzii*, et *Licmophora flabellata* were encountered by [8] from subtropical mangroves environments in Mexico. It could be linked to their euryhaline nature because according to [24] diatoms are the most representative group of algae in these areas in relation to the euryhaline nature of the majority of these taxa.

Species like *Delphineis surirella*, *Grammatophora oceanica* et *Grammatophora marina* have been found in phytoplankton by [7, 16] and others like *Rhabdonema adriaticum*, *Ardissonia robusta*, *Grammatophora oceanica*, *Licmophora ehrenbergii*, *Toxarium undulatum* in phytobenthos by [8, 17]. In benthic diatoms, forms with true raphe have a higher binding capacity, due to the excretion of mucilaginous substances through this raphe [25]. However, the taxa described here are araphids. But, according to [20], when diatoms do not have a raphe, the adhesion of the valve can take place thanks to the secretion of extracellular mucilaginous substances by other parts of the frustule or by the pseudoraphe characteristic of most species of Fragilariophyceae. This could explain their presence in both phytoplankton and phytobenthos.

4. Conclusion

The descriptive study of Ngor's diatoms showed 18 taxa of araphid pennate diatoms distributed in 9 genera, 9 families, 8 orders and one class. It has contributed to the creation of a database of diatomic communities. The knowledge of the diversity level of diatom in Ngor will allow further studies such as the use of diatomic index methods and therefore a very reliable assessment of the biological quality of the water.

Compliance with ethical standards

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